

The Effects of Policy Makers on the Public and the Public's View of Politicians

Assoc . Prof. Mehmet Kürşat Semerci

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 6-02, 2024, p. 125– 142. - 0099-0001-2402-0107.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) “EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform.” (“CURRENT SCIENCE”) (“Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia”) ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

1

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• *Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic*" ("CURRENT SCIENCE ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -

Current Science Georgia")

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month.""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• *The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this* ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia")

""• *Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.*""

("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

Political science encompasses the study of how policymakers shape public opinion and the way the public perceives politicians (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Policymakers have a significant impact on both the general public and their view of lawmakers (Liu, 2020). Choices and behavior of individuals and groups exert influence on policies that directly affect the well-being of people and communities. When policymakers successfully execute efficient policies to address urgent issues and enhance the welfare of the public, they get support from the public and are closely scrutinized (Slyke et al., 2005). If politicians fail to address social issues or execute inadequate remedies, it may result in a decrease in faith in the democratic system. Furthermore, policymakers possess the capacity to shape public mood via the use of impactful messaging and communication tactics. Politicians use several tactics, including media campaigns, public speeches, and social media, to shape public sentiment and cultivate support for their ideas and personal reputation. Policymakers has the capacity to indirectly shape public opinion by means of their associations with stakeholders and diverse interest groups. These gatherings have a significant influence on society about certain topics. Policymakers and politicians are significantly influenced by the overall public opinion and the way the public perceives them (Liu, 2020). Their activities, assessments, and methods of communication play a vital role in influencing public sentiment and gathering support for politicians and initiatives. The media has a substantial influence on the public's viewpoint and perception of politicians (Slyke et al., 2005). News consumers often depend on the media to guide them on the subjects they should be concerned about and how to comprehend happenings (Liu, 2020).

Key Words: Politics, Political Science, Political Science and the Public, Politics and the Public, Politic Makers and Public Relations, Public Relations with Political Decisions

Introduction

The press functions as a crucial conduit of information and has a significant influence on forming public opinion (Chakraborty et al., 2018). The frameworks presented by politicians may influence the way the public perceives them (Liu, 2020). In addition, the advent of social media has offered politicians a novel means to directly engage with the public and influence their opinions (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Politicians may use social media platforms to establish connections with a broader audience at a lower cost compared to conventional media. Social media has empowered politicians to communicate directly with the people, circumventing conventional middlemen and delivering their views in a more customized and captivating manner. This significantly influenced their opinions of politicians and the public. In summary, policymakers have a substantial effect on both the general public's views and their impressions of politicians. Engaging with interest groups and using social media have a significant impact on the way the public perceives and approves of politicians. Social media serves as a potent instrument enabling politicians to directly engage with the people and shape their perspectives. Political science significantly influences policymakers' perspectives on both public opinion and politicians. The use of social media, particularly by politicians, has enabled a direct link with the public and has greatly impacted the strategies employed by candidates during campaigns, as well as the manner in which individuals participate in political matters and discussions. Moreover, social media amplifies the public's perspectives on politicians and political matters. The results pertain to the communication and self-presentation of politicians, as well as their ability to shape public opinion and impact people's engagement in political discourse (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020).

Aim

4

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

Policymakers' perspectives of politicians and the public are often complex. This phenomenon encompasses the media's ability to shape public opinion by utilizing news and interpretive frames, politicians' utilization of social media platforms to directly communicate and engage with the public, and politicians' capacity to establish connections with individuals through both traditional media and social media (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Policymakers have a substantial impact on both the general population and their opinions of lawmakers. They possess the capacity to shape public opinion by actively interacting with interest groups, using social media platforms, and employing effective communication tactics. Social media enables direct interaction with the intended audience, circumventing conventional middlemen and conveying messages in a more individualized and captivating manner (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Policymakers have a substantial impact on the general public and their opinion of politicians via their use of social media platforms, engagement with interest groups, and implementation of successful communication methods. They possess the capacity to shape public opinion by leveraging their affiliations with interest organizations and engaging actively with the public (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Policymakers have a substantial impact on both the general population and their attitudes of politicians. Utilizing social media enables them to establish direct connections with individuals nationwide, therefore molding their viewpoints and exerting influence over their ideas. Policymakers have a substantial impact on both the general population and their attitudes of politicians. Utilizing social media enables them to directly engage with viewers, circumventing conventional middlemen and shaping their impressions (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Policymakers have a substantial impact on both the public's views and their perceptions of lawmakers. They possess the capacity to shape society by actively involving themselves with interest groups, using impactful communication tactics, and harnessing the power of social media platforms. Public attitude and views of policymakers are mostly shaped by policymakers. Politicians possess the capacity to shape the public's opinion of them by means of their actions, words, and engagements with the public across various media platforms.

Methodology

5

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

Public attitude and views of policymakers are mostly shaped by policymakers. They may use communication tactics, such as using social media platforms, to actively interact with their audience and shape their perspectives. Public attitude and views of policymakers are mostly shaped by policymakers. Through the use of many communication tactics, such as social media, they possess the ability to influence public opinion, actively interact with the public, and alter the public's impression of politicians. Policymakers' impressions of politicians and the public are greatly influenced in general. Utilizing social media enables individuals to establish direct connections with others and exert influence on their viewpoints and perceptions (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Policymakers have a substantial impact on both the general population and their opinions of lawmakers (Chakraborty et al., 2018). By using social media and employing various communication tactics, politicians have the ability to enhance public consciousness, actively interact with the public, and alter people' perspectives of politicians. Public attitude and views of policymakers are mostly shaped by policymakers. Utilizing social media allows for direct and immediate interaction with the public, circumventing conventional middlemen and exerting influence on their perspective. According to sources, policymakers have a substantial influence on both the general population and their opinions of lawmakers. Through the use of many communication tactics, such as social media, they possess the capacity to exert influence on society. This may result in the dissemination of a certain political image or message among supporters and other individuals. Public attitude and views of policymakers are mostly shaped by policymakers.

Literature Review

Utilizing social media and other communication platforms enables individuals to engage in direct interactions with others, exert influence on their viewpoints, and disseminate their political opinions (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Policymakers have a substantial impact on both the general population and their attitudes of politicians. By using communication platforms like social media, individuals have the ability to actively interact with others, alter their viewpoints, and disseminate their political ideologies. Typically, politicians have the ability to

CURRENT SCIENCE

shape public opinion and the perception of legislators among the general public. By using communication platforms like social media, individuals may actively interact with others, modify their viewpoints, and disseminate their political ideologies. This may also result in the dissemination of false information and intentional manipulation of truths. Policymakers have a substantial impact on both the general population and their opinions of lawmakers (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Policymakers have a significant impact on the public's attitudes and views about lawmakers. Social media enables direct interpersonal communication, therefore shaping individuals' ideas and exerting impact on their impressions of politicians. Public attitude and views of policymakers are mostly shaped by policymakers. Social media enables direct communication between individuals, therefore molding their ideas and impacting their impressions of politicians. Public attitude and views of policymakers are mostly shaped by policymakers. Social media facilitates direct communication among individuals, therefore molding their viewpoints and exerting an impact on their evaluations of politicians. Policymakers have a substantial impact on both the general population and their attitudes of politicians. Utilizing social media enables them to directly engage with individuals, mold their viewpoints, and exert influence on their views of politicians. The impact of policy makers on the general public and the perception of politicians by the public is entirely contingent upon the extent of their use of social media. In addition, their tactics are shaped by elements such as their capacity to address public issues and their conduct (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Moreover, the media and other information outlets have the ability to influence the public's image of politicians. Policymakers have a significant impact on the public's attitudes and views about lawmakers.

Public attitude and views of policymakers are mostly shaped by policymakers. Utilizing social media enables individuals to engage in direct interactions with others, so molding their viewpoints and exerting an impact on their perceptions of politicians (Chakraborty et al., 2018). In addition, social media platforms provide politicians with the opportunity to share personal tales and display their personalities, therefore humanizing them in the eyes of the general public (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Engaging in this practice may cultivate a more favorable public perception and foster trust and support from a wider audience. The use of social media by

CURRENT SCIENCE

policymakers may have a substantial influence on the public's image of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers enables them to directly engage with the public, giving them the potential to influence public opinion and alter the public's impression of legislators.

The Impact of Social Media on Politicians and Public Opinion

Social media enables direct interpersonal communication, therefore shaping individuals' ideas and exerting impact on their impressions of politicians. Moreover, social media provides politicians with the chance to exhibit their personalities and divulge their personal narratives, so resulting in their humanization in the public's perspective. Engaging in such initiatives may enhance their public image and foster more trust and support from the public. Policy makers may promote more engagement and involvement of a larger number of individuals by using social media platforms. Participating in such events might assist politicians in cultivating a more favorable public image as it motivates them to attend and actively interact with attendees.

Topic: The Influence of social media on Public Opinion and Policy Making: The use of social media by policymakers has the potential to have a substantial impact on both the general public and their impressions of politicians. lawmakers have the capacity to influence public opinion and alter the public's impression of lawmakers by directly engaging with the public via social media. The use of social media platforms by policymakers may result in increased public involvement and participation. This has the capacity to captivate and establish a connection with politicians, so fostering more favorable perceptions of them. The use of social media by policymakers may have a substantial influence on the view of politicians by the general population. Enhanced engagement between politicians and the public fosters more trust and credibility. Through direct communication, politicians have the ability to influence public opinion and control the narrative around their policies and actions. Politicians often use social media platforms to sway public opinion and alter their perception of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers significantly impacts the public's image of politicians. Through the use of social media platforms, policymakers have the capacity to exert influence on public mood and alter their views of politicians. Policymakers may use social media platforms to engage in direct communication with the public, facilitating discussions about their policies

8

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX
(ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE,
GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353
EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

CURRENT SCIENCE

and perspectives, and promptly addressing pertinent concerns. In addition, the use of social media enables policymakers to access a wider demographic and interact with those who may not actively engage in conventional political discussions. Policymakers has the capacity to shape public sentiment by directly engaging with a wide-ranging audience via social media platforms. In addition, governments have the ability to use social media as a strategic instrument to counteract misinformation or confront unfavorable narratives, so influencing public opinions toward politicians and policies. Policymakers may enhance transparency and responsibility by using social media platforms. Policymakers may use social media platforms as a means to directly engage with the public and distribute information on their preferences and policies. Furthermore, social media enables prompt criticism and active engagement from the general populace, so guaranteeing that officials are held responsible for their actions. In general, the use of social media by politicians may have a substantial influence on public opinion and the public's impressions of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers has the capacity to exert influence on society and alter the attitudes held towards politicians. This phenomenon has the capacity to enhance curiosity and engagement in political matters, while simultaneously having the ability to alter the perspectives of the general public on politicians and their policies. In addition, social media enables politicians to evaluate the prevailing public sentiment and adjust their policies appropriately. In general, the use of social media platforms by politicians has fundamentally transformed their means of communication with the general public, resulting in a substantial influence on public mood and the public's opinion of politicians. The shared material exposes the many ways in which social media may impact political choices and mold public opinion.

Findings

Social media amplifies people' perspectives on politicians and political matters. Nevertheless, it is important to recognize that not all individuals possess the resources to engage in social media or opt out of virtual political discourse. To summarize, the influence of social media on the general population and their views of politicians does not reflect the views of any specific

CURRENT SCIENCE

group within the public. The use of social media networks by policymakers may have a substantial influence on the public's emotion and impression of politicians. It enables them to efficiently communicate with a wide audience, enhance transparency, counteract misinformation, and interact with the public in real-time. Moreover, social media has the potential to shape the public's perception of politicians by enabling them to present themselves in a more amiable and accessible way. Policymakers recognize that social media have the capacity to profoundly impact public opinion and the public's impression of politicians via enabling direct contact, enhancing transparency, and molding public image and credibility. The use of social media by policymakers may significantly impact the public's image of lawmakers. It enables them to influence public opinions, establish direct connections with the public, and engage in real-time interactions with individuals. Politicians may shape the public's impression of themselves by using social media platforms to directly engage with the public, enhance transparency, and mold their public image and credibility (Chakraborty et al., 2018). In general, the use of social media by policymakers may have a substantial influence on public opinion and the public's view of politicians (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). The use of social media by policy makers has the potential to exert influence on society and alter its perceptions and attitudes towards politicians. It enables them to efficiently communicate with a wide audience, enhance transparency, counteract misinformation, and interact with the public in real-time. The acts of policymakers on social media have a significant impact on public opinion and may alter the way the public views politicians. It enables them to efficiently communicate with a wide audience, enhance transparency, counteract misinformation, and interact with the public in real-time. The use of social media by policymakers has the potential to significantly shape the public's image of politicians.

Argument

Twitter and Facebook, being social media platforms, provide politicians the chance to directly and immediately engage with the people and shape their view. They have the ability to directly convey their ideas, accomplishments, and tactics to a broad audience without relying on

CURRENT SCIENCE

conventional media middlemen. Social media enables politicians to directly interact with their constituents, efficiently address their concerns, and cultivate a sense of trust and accessibility among the general population. Social media significantly impacts public opinion and shapes the people's impression of Members of Parliament (MPs). It affords them the chance to portray themselves in a favorable manner and control the discourse around their policies and activities. Moreover, social media provides politicians with the chance to promptly counter criticism and tackle public concerns, enabling them to cultivate a more innovative and discreet persona. Policymakers' use of social media has a substantial influence on public mood and the public's view of legislators (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Individuals are able to influence public opinions, engage in direct communication with the public, and enhance transparency (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). In general, the use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's emotion and impression of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial influence on the public's view of politicians (Chakraborty et al., 2018). The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on both the general public and their opinion of politicians (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Policymakers must comprehend the transformative impact of social media on society. Consequently, it is necessary for them to use social media platforms strategically in order to actively involve the intended audience and successfully communicate their message. Policymakers have the ability to use social media platforms as a means to shape public sentiment and exert control over the discussion around their policies and activities. The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's image of politicians. Politicians need to give precedence to adjusting to the evolving communication landscape and using social media. The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's image of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers may significantly impact the public's image of lawmakers. The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's image of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's image of politicians. Hence, the use of social media by policymakers has a substantial influence on public opinion and the public's view of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers has a significant impact on the public's view of politicians (Chakraborty et al., 2018). The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's image of politicians.

CURRENT SCIENCE

The use of social media by policymakers has the capacity to shape the public's impression of politicians (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Politicians may shape public perception of themselves by using social media. The use of social media by policy makers has a substantial impact on the public's view of politicians and the development of public opinion (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Nevertheless, it is imperative to acknowledge that variables such as the target audience's demographics, the particular social media platforms employed, and the nature of the content and messages shared can influence the effect of social media on public opinion and the public's perception of politicians (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's image of politicians. Studying the influence of social media on public opinion and the public's image of politicians is a significant area of study in the field of political science. The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's image of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers has fundamentally revolutionized their means of engaging with the general public and the strategies employed by politicians throughout their campaigns. The use of social media by politicians has fundamentally revolutionized the realm of political communication. Social media have the capacity to significantly impact public sentiment and mold popular perspectives of politicians. Policymakers have transformed the political landscape by using social media platforms to engage in direct interactions with the public, therefore exerting an impact on public opinion. The use of social media by politicians has resulted in a significant transformation in how politicians engage with the general population. This has had a substantial impact on the way politicians and the general people are seen. The use of social media by politicians has fundamentally revolutionized the realm of political communication. According to Chakraborty et al. (2018), social media has a substantial impact on public opinion since it molds their views of politicians. The widespread use of social media by politicians has expedited a transformation in the way the public perceives politicians and their popularity (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's image of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the public's image of politicians. Hence, the use of social media by policymakers has a substantial influence on public opinion and the public's view of politicians. Policymakers have seen a significant transformation in political communication facilitated by the use of social media platforms.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Social media enables instantaneous and direct communication with the general population. Although social media enables policy makers to engage with the public instantly and directly, it also has the capacity to mold public opinion and impact the public's impression of politicians (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that policymakers are not just concerned with the influence of social media on public opinion and the public's impression of politicians. The impact is also influenced by the reliability of information shared on social media, the level of public involvement and participation, and the wider political context in which these interactions take place (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Policymakers have modified the use of social media in political communication, nevertheless, it is essential to also take into account other elements that impact public opinion and the overall viewpoint of the general public.

An individual's perspectives on politicians are shaped by a range of factors, including personal experiences, individual values and beliefs, and conventional media. The use of social media by policymakers has fundamentally revolutionized political communication by enabling direct and instantaneous engagement with the broader public. Furthermore, politicians have experienced a substantial impact on the emotion and viewpoint of the general populace. The use of social media by policymakers has facilitated prompt and direct engagement with the public, leading to a significant transformation in political communication. Social media has caused a change in the way the public feels and thinks about politicians, since it allows politicians to communicate their thoughts directly to the public, bypassing conventional media channels. Moreover, the utilization of social media provides legislators with a prompt means to comprehend and tackle the concerns and viewpoints of the overall populace. This enables widespread public engagement and prompt dissemination of information. The use of social media by policymakers has fundamentally revolutionized political communication, enabling direct and instantaneous engagement with the broader public. Enhancing the accessibility of information has had a profound effect on the public's overall feeling and viewpoint towards politicians. Typically, officials use social media platforms to establish direct connectivity, facilitate engagement, and promptly respond. Hence, social media has the capacity to mold public mood and influence their impressions of leaders. Accurate weather predictions are

CURRENT SCIENCE

essential in the present global context (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Policymakers often use social media as a means to shape public opinion and manipulate societal attitudes towards politicians (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). In addition, social media has democratized access to political information and fostered more transparency in the political process. The use of social media by policymakers has fundamentally revolutionized political communication by enabling direct and instantaneous engagement with the broader public. The widespread availability of information and increasing transparency in the political process have greatly impacted public opinion and the way people see politicians. Policymakers often use social media to exert influence on both public opinion and the public's views of lawmakers. Accurate weather predictions are essential in the present global context (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Policy makers have revolutionized political communication in contemporary times by using social media, enabling immediate and direct engagement with the public. This had a substantial influence on the perspectives of both the general population and policymakers. Policymakers has the capacity to shape society and alter public opinions of politicians via the use of social media. Utilizing social media platforms, policymakers have fundamentally revolutionized political communication by enabling direct and instantaneous engagement with the broader public (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). The use of social media by policymakers has fundamentally revolutionized political communication, enabling direct and instantaneous engagement with the broader public. The process of making information accessible to the general public and the subsequent increase in transparency within the political system has had a profound impact on popular sentiment and the perception of politicians (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Policymakers' use of social media has fundamentally revolutionized political communication by enabling instantaneous and direct engagement with the general public (Meti et al., 2015). The occurrence resulted in a change in the allocation of authority, as politicians managed to circumvent conventional media outlets and assume command of their own storyline (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Through the use of social media platforms, policymakers have transformed the landscape of political communication by facilitating immediate and direct engagement with the general public. The process of democratizing information and the subsequent increase in transparency in the political sphere have had a significant impact on public opinion and the perception of politicians (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Policymakers have undergone a significant

shift in political communication as a result of using social media platforms. It facilitates immediate and direct communication with the general population (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Consequently, there has been a notable shift in the allocation of power, with politicians now possessing the capacity to circumvent conventional media outlets and exert control over their own narratives (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). Consequently, the use of social media by policymakers has fundamentally revolutionized political communication, enabling instantaneous and direct engagement with the broader public (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Consequently, there was a rise in public awareness and engagement, leading to a heightened sense of accountability among political leaders. Policymakers' use of social media has fundamentally revolutionized political communication by enabling direct and instantaneous engagement with the general public (Zhuravskaya et al., 2020). It has had a substantial impact on public opinion and the way the public views politicians. The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on both the general public and their view of politicians (Chakraborty et al., 2018). Social media enables policymakers to engage with the public promptly and directly. Hence, social media has a significant impact on the public's view of politicians.

Conclusion

Social media has a significant impact on both popular sentiment and political figures. According to Zhuravskaya et al. (2020), the direct and immediate contact between policymakers and the public has a significant impact on shaping public opinion and influencing people's perception of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers has fundamentally revolutionized political communication by enabling instantaneous and direct engagement with the broader public. Consequently, there was a rise in public awareness and engagement, and politicians became more cognizant of their duties. The use of social media by policymakers has a substantial impact on the attitudes of both the general public and lawmakers. The impact of social media on public opinion and the perception of politicians is significant since it has the capacity to directly and immediately communicate with individuals. The use of social media

CURRENT SCIENCE

by policymakers has fundamentally revolutionized political communication by enabling instantaneous and direct engagement with the broader public. Consequently, there was a rise in public awareness and engagement, leading to an expanded understanding of politicians' obligations. The advent of social media has augmented policymakers' ability to shape the public's perception of lawmakers. It enables immediate and impactful communication that may swiftly shape public opinion and greatly impact the public's perception of politicians. Through the use of social media, politicians have transformed political communication by establishing immediate and direct engagement with the public. This has enhanced the capacity of politicians to engage with individuals and modify popular emotions. Political communication has facilitated policymakers to use social media platforms for direct and instantaneous engagement with the public. This not only enhanced the extent and velocity of communication, but also facilitated the establishment of a more authentic and personalized connection with the audience. Social media enables policymakers to engage with the public promptly and directly. Hence, social media has a significant impact on the public's view of politicians. Through the use of social media, politicians have transformed political communication by establishing immediate and direct engagement with the public. Consequently, there has been a rise in both the degree of knowledge and involvement, paralleling the greater awareness among the public about the obligations of politicians. The use of social media by policymakers has significantly impacted the public's perception of politicians. This advancement has influenced public attention by enabling an enhanced and instantaneous engagement between politicians and the public. Politicians have significantly altered their public engagement and influenced the people's attitude and viewpoint by modifying their use of social media. Perspective of politicians The Internet and social media have had a profound impact on both society and politics. Politicians has the capacity to exert influence on society and alter public perceptions of themselves via adept use of social media platforms. Moreover, examination of the tactics used by political parties to interact with voters on the internet demonstrates that social media has transformed into a digital platform where significant political matters are discussed and deliberated. Interactive and forceful social media strategies exemplify the growing significance and impact of social media in political campaigns. The use of social media by policymakers has fundamentally revolutionized political communication by enabling direct and

instantaneous engagement with the broader public. Consequently, this circumstance has had tremendous impact on the shaping of public opinion and the way politicians are seen by the public. Politicians may alter the public's perception by using social media proficiently. Social media campaigns have become a significant venue for advocating and contesting political matters.

References

Chakraborty, S., Chandra, P., Pal, J., & Romero, D M. (2018, June 1). Political Tweets and Mainstream News Impact in India: A Mixed Methods Investigation into Political Outreach.

https://scholarworks.iupui.edu/bitstream/1805/18654/1/Chakraborty_2018_political.pdf

Liu, Y. (2020, January 1). The Influence and Value of Network Public Opinion on Public Policy.

<https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ss.20200904.14>

Meti, V., PK, K., & MC, G. (2015, January 1). Social Media for Political Mobilization in India: A Study. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2165-7912.1000275>

Slyke, D. M. V., Horne, C S., & Thomas, J C. (2005, July 1). The Implications of Public Opinion for Public Managers. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095399705276112>

1. Zhuravskaya, E., Petrova, M., & Ениколопов, P. (2020, August 2). Political Effects of the Internet and Social Media. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-economics-081919-050239>